

ADDITIONAL VERIFICATION METHODS

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Abstract: In this article, we looked at additional verification methods

Key words: Additional, methods, research methods.

Additional methods of examination of a dental patient include:

- thermometry;
- electrometric method (electrodontodiagnostics);
- a photo;
- functional methods;
- general somatic methods;
- neurological methods;
- radiological methods;
- laboratory (general clinical, biochemical, serological, cytological, histological, microbiological);
- histomorphological methods;
- specific studies in the oral cavity.

Thermometric research methods

In this study, heat and cold are used to determine the reaction of dental tissues. Using these methods, it is possible to make a differential diagnosis between caries and pulpitis (inflammation of the soft tissues inside the tooth), pulpitis and periodontitis (inflammation of the ligament holding the tooth in the well). To conduct the study, a wet swab cooled with ether or water after melting ice is applied to the dried surface of the tooth, or hot gutta-percha is applied. If it is hot (for incisors, for example, more than 50° C) or cold (for incisors, for example, less than 22° C) pain occurs, but within a few seconds after the removal of the stimulus, it passes, then this is a normal pulp reaction. If the pain stops after 10-15 seconds or more, then this indicates pulp hyperemia or reversible inflammation. Severe pain from the irritant, which continues even after their elimination, indicates irreversible pulpitis, in which complete removal of the pulp is indicated. Pain arising from heat, but quickly ceasing from cold, also indicates irreversible pulpitis. The lack of reaction to temperature samples indicates that the pulp is already necrotic.

Electrodontodiagnostics

Electrodontodiagnostics (EDI) is the determination of the reaction of the nerve receptors of the pulp to an electric current. The technique was developed by L.R.

Rubin, but back in 1866 A. Maigtió proposed using electric current to diagnose caries. Electrodontodiagnostics allows us to judge the qualitative and quantitative disorders in the tooth pulp. These electrodontodiagnostics are used in differential diagnosis and monitoring of the effectiveness of the treatment.

Indications for the use of electrodontodiagnostics:

- deep caries;
- pulpitis;
- change your clothes;
- periodontitis;
- radicular cyst;
- injury to teeth and jaw;
- sinusitis;
- osteomyelitis;
- swelling of the jaws;
- neuritis of the facial and trigeminal nerves;
- orthodontic interventions.

Functional research methods are auxiliary diagnostic tools that identify early, hidden signs of the disease and the stages of its development, determine indications for pathogenetic therapy, monitor the effectiveness of treatment and predict its outcome.

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